

Population Density and Frequency of Occurrence of Commercial Sea Cucumbers Species in Danao, Panglao, Bohol

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Abstract

The study was made to determine the species composition, population density and relative abundance of sea cucumber species in the intertidal area of barangay Danao, Panglao, Bohol. The collection of sea cucumber species was done during low tide. In the collection, 800 square meters' belt transect was used. *Actinopyga*, *Bohadschia*, *Holothuria*, and *Pearsonothuria* were the four genera observed. There were only two species under genus *Actinopyga* with species *A. caroliniana* and *A. echinites*. Under genus *Bohadschia* three species were collected and were identified as *B. marmorata* and *B. vitiensis*. The majority were *Holothurians* species which includes *H. atra*, *H. aff atra*, *H. coluber*, *H. fuscocineria*, *H. Hilla*, *H. impatiens*, *H. lineata*, *H. rigida*, *H. scabra*, and *H. turriscelsa*. Under genus *Pearsonothuria* only one species was identified and named as *P. graeffeii*. Among the 94 *holothurians*, *Holothuria atra* had the highest density with 19 individuals per 25,600 square meters. second with the highest population density was the species of *Holothuria fuscocineria*, with 17 individuals per 25,600 square meters. This was followed by *Holothuria scabra* with 11 individuals per 25,600 square meters. Meanwhile, the species with a high frequency of occurrence was *Holothuria atra* with 56%, followed by *H. fuscocineria* with 53% and *H. scabra* with 34% respectively. Result of the study showed that the majority of commercial sea cucumber species were of low population density and occurrence. Hence, there is a need for continuous monitoring of the population status of these species as they are of high marketable value

Keywords-Assessment, *Aspidochirote*, *Echinodermata*, *Holothurians*, *Marine Resources*

I. Introduction

Commercial sea cucumbers are detritivores, a role in the marine ecosystem that conducts functions like nutrient recycling and bioturbation (Uthicke, 2003). Several species of sea cucumbers are symbionts of molluscs and pearlfishes that may disappear once a species are overexploited (Bruckner, 2005). They are also considered as a good source of protein for humans containing 55% and lower in fat compared to other food. They are also used in pharmaceutical and cosmetic industries (Subaldo, 2011). Moreover, they served as an important source of livelihood for many of the coastal communities in the archipelago by exporting trepang or dried sea cucumber (Gamboa, 2004).

Despite their ecological and economic importance, sea cucumber populations are vulnerable to decline because of rampant exploitation, ever-increasing market demand, and inadequacy of fishery management (Conand, 2005). The Philippines is one of the important sea cucumber fishing countries that have no pertinent national management or regulatory measures for sea cucumbers (Labe, 2007). Data on the abundance of the sea cucumber population is still limited (FAO, 2008).

In Panglao particularly in Danao, there are no studies on sea cucumber documented. Thus, baseline studies on the population density and frequency of occurrence of sea cucumbers are important to provide the information needed for conservation and management of sea cucumbers in the said area. Hence this study was made mainly to determine the population status of sea cucumber species in terms of their density and occurrence. The method used in the study was a belt transect method because of the patchy behavior of these species. The outcome of the study will be the basis of formulating laws and regulations pertaining to the massive collection of these wild marine resources.

II. Materials and Methods

Barangay Danao, Panglao, Bohol is located at 9°34'44'' N and 123°45' 00''E with a total land area of 789.65 hectares. It has an intertidal area of approximately 280,000 m² (1400m width x 200m length). In most of the littoral zone, dense seagrasses and some patches of algae were found. It is part of Municipality of Panglao which is a fourth class municipality in the province of Bohol. It is located in the southwestern part at 9°34'44'' North, 123° 44'45'' East with an area of 5, 537. The island is politically divided into two municipalities: Daus and Panglao. The town of Panglao consists of ten barangays and Danao is the largest barangay.

The method used in the collection of sea cucumbers was a belt transect method, adopted from the work of Bourgoin *et al.*, 2005 with modifications. In the work of Bourgoin *et al.*, 2005, 50 meters transect was laid with one meter in both sides and transect distance five meters apart was used in the collection of holothuroids. However, in this study, 200 meters transect was laid perpendicular to the shore. All sea cucumbers present within two meters to the right and two meters to the left of the transect were collected. The total area of the belt transect is 800 m². All sea cucumber observed within the belt transect were handpicked. The collection was done during lowest lowtide preferably during the evening because of its tendency to burrow during the day.

Identification of the specimens was based on FAO Identification Keys of Holothuroidea by Conand (1990), Illustrated Key to Sea cucumber by Pawson *et al.*, 2008 a Sea Cucumbers of American Samoa by Atafua *et al.*, 2008 and Survey on Shallow -Sea Cucumber of Central Philippines by Kerr *et al.*, 2006. Spicules were also observed using a compound microscope to really specify the species of sea cucumbers.

III. Results and Discussions

A. Population Density

Among the 17 species observed in the intertidal area of Barangay Danao, Panglao, Bohol, *Holothuria atra* had the highest density with 19 individuals per 25,600 square meters (Table 1). These species were observed in sandy substrates associated with sea grass beds. Variability in the food supply was the major controlling factor in population dynamics of the benthic animals, particularly the holothurians (Jumars *et al.*, 1986). According to Dar *et al.*, 2006, the deposit feeding holothurians were the dominant megafauna, in terms of both number and biomass in many littoral ecosystems and on sheltered marine shallow waters substrates. Since *Holothuria atra* were deposit feeders, they tend to mix with sediments on seagrass beds to consume detritus, bacteria, and diatoms (Conand, 2006). Studies of Uthicke *et al.*, 1999 also added that *Holothuria atra* exhibited no preference for any food type. These could be the reasons why they were the species with the highest population density in the study area.

This second with the highest population density was the species of *Holothuria fuscocineria*, with 17 individuals per 25,600 square meters. In this study, *Holothuria fuscocineria* were found in sea grass beds. These species were commonly observed in low energy environments where nutrient settlements are high (Mercier *et al.*, 2000).

This was followed by *Holothuria scabra* with 11 individuals per 25,600 square meters. This was found in sandy areas with sea grasses. *Holothuria scabra* is detritivore and they occur mainly in low energy environments behind fringing reefs or within protected bays and shores (Mercier *et al.*, 2000). This animal is known to tolerate low salinity by burying and lowering their cloacal pumping frequency (Mercier *et al.*, 1999). In addition, *Holothuria scabra* have no food preference as suggested by James (1989).

Table 1. Population Density of Sea cucumber Species in the Intertidal area of Danao, Panglao, Bohol

SPECIES NAME	NO. OF INDIVIDUALS	POPULATION DENSITY
<i>A. caroliniana</i>	2	2/25600 m ²
<i>A. echinites</i>	2	2/25600 m ²
<i>Bohadschia argus</i>	1	1/25600 m ²
<i>B. marmorata</i>	7	7/25600 m ²
<i>B. vitiensis</i>	2	2/25600
<i>Holothuria atra</i>	19	19/25600 m ²
<i>Holothuria aff atra</i>	8	8/25600 m ²
<i>Holothuria coluber</i>	5	5/25600 m ²
<i>H. fuscocineria</i>	17	17/25600 m ²
<i>Holothuria hilla</i>	2	2/25600 m ²
<i>H. impatiens</i>	3	3/25600 m ²
<i>Holothuria lineata</i>	1	1/25600 m ²
<i>H. pervicax</i>	4	4/25600 m ²
<i>Holothuria rigida</i>	2	2/25600 m ²
<i>Holothuria scabra</i>	11	11/25600 m ²
<i>H. turriscelsa</i>	6	6/25600 m ²
<i>P. graeffeii</i>	2	2/25600 m ²

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The species with also low densities were *Holothuria aff atra* with only eight, *Holothuria coluber* with five individuals, *Holothuria pervicax* with four individuals, *Holothuria turriscelsa* with six individuals, *Holothuria impatiens* three individuals and *Bohadschia marmorata* with seven individuals collected in the study area.

The species with the lowest densities with only one or two individuals collected were *Actinopyga caroliniana*, *Actinopyga echinites*, *Holothuria rigida*, *Pearsonothuria graeffeii*, *Bohadschia argus*, *Bohadschia vitiensis*, and *Holothuria lineata*. These species were all under Order Aspidochirotida. This result is the same result with the study of Kerr *et al.*, 2006 in Bolinao and Anda, Pangasinan was all sea cucumber species belonged to Order Aspidochirotida were of low density. Their low densities could be attributed by low food availability in the study site which influenced their reproduction (Uthicke, 2001).

Furthermore, the recorded low population density in many of the Aspidochirote holothurians was more likely caused by commercial fishery and cyclone damage since they were dependent on the success of fertilization. The recent terrestrial and coastal development may have resulted in the loss of preferred settlement areas or unfavorable environmental factors, such as variation in salinity, pH and toxins in the water column. These factors showed to affect spawning as well as larval settlement and development. Thus, a decrease in recruitment of holothuroids may be expected in disturbed coastal areas (Ashen *et al.*, 2005).

B. Frequency of Occurrence

Table 2 shows that the species of *Holothuria atra* were the most frequently occurring species throughout the 32 transects with 56% frequency. These species were commonly found on low energy environments where nutrient settlements were high (Conand *et al.*, 2006). In addition, the high occurrence of *Holothuria atra* could be attributed by the surrounding conditions as; the nature of the bottom sediments, their degree of tolerance in the exposure at low tide time, benthic community's distribution (corals and algal cover) food availability and may be degree of pollution (Dar,2002).

The second species with a high frequency of occurrence was the *Holothuria fuscocineria* species with 53% value. And followed by *Holothuria scabra* with 34 % occurrence. According to the study of Mercier *et al.*, 2000, deposit feeder, holothurians mostly occur in areas where sediments comprise about 5-10% organic matter. In that study, it was also described that later larval stages of *Holothuria scabra* settle on sea grasses. This could be the reason why they mostly occur in sea grass beds in the study area.

On the other hand, *Bohadschia argus*, *Bohadschia citzens*, *Bohadschia marmorata*, *Actinopyga caroliniana*, *Actinopyga echinites*, *Pearsonothuria graeffeii*, *Holothuria rigida*, *Holothuria hilla*, *Holothuria pervicax*, *Holothuria impatiens*, *Holothuria turriscelsa*, and *Holothuria lineata* were the species that was rarely observed in the area. Some of these species are nocturnal like the *Bohadschia* genera and others were also cryptic like most of the *Holothuria* genera that could be the reason on their frequency of occurrence (Kerr *et al.*, 2006). Futhermore, Zenkerith (1963) stated that holothurians comprise a high percentage of total biomass in deep waters of about 90% and only 10% in shallow areas. This could explain why their frequency of occurrence in the intertidal area was low.

Table 2. Frequency of Occurrence of Seventeen Holothuroid Species in the Intertidal area of Danao, Panglao, Bohol

Species Name	Number of Occurrence	Frequency of Occurrence
<i>Actinopyga caroliniana</i>	2	6%
<i>Actinopyga echinites</i>	2	6%
<i>Bohadschia argus</i>	1	3%
<i>Bohadschia marmorata</i>	6	19%
<i>Bohadschia vitiensis</i>	2	6%
<i>Holothuria atra</i>	18	56%
<i>Holothuria aff atra</i>	8	25%
<i>Holothuria coluber</i>	5	16%
<i>Holothuria fuscocineria</i>	17	53%
<i>Holothuria hilla</i>	2	6%
<i>Holothuria impatiens</i>	3	9%
<i>Holothuria lineata</i>	1	3%
<i>Holothuria pervicax</i>	4	13%
<i>Holothuria scabra</i>	11	34%
<i>Holothuria rigida</i>	2	6%
<i>Holothuria turriscelsa</i>	6	19%
<i>P. graeffeii</i>	2	6%

IV. Conclusion

Population density and frequency of occurrence of sea cucumber species were mainly influenced by their commercial value and mode of reproduction. Majority of the species have low population density which means that they were heavily exploited in the area. Hence, there is a need for regular monitoring of these wild stocks in Danao, Panglao Bohol. Considering the boost of the economy in the area, there is a great possibility that these marine resources may be affected.

V. Recommendations

1. The study on their spawning period would also be interesting to further know the factors that influenced their abundance.
2. Lastly, studying sea cucumber species around Bohol especially the highly commercialized species is very important to assess the present condition of sea cucumber species.

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